

1 **Human Tissue Distribution of Anidulafungin and Micafungin**

2 Jana Marx,^a René Welte,^a Tiziana Gasperetti,^a Patrizia Moser,^{b*} Michael Joannidis,^c and
3 Romuald Bellmann^{a#}

4 ^aClinical Pharmacokinetics Unit, Division of Intensive Care and Emergency Medicine,
5 Department of Internal Medicine I, Medical University of Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria

6 ^bDepartment of Pathology, Medical University of Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria

7 ^cDivision of Intensive Care and Emergency Medicine, Department Internal Medicine I,
8 Medical University of Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria

9 *Present address: INNPATh GmbH, Tirol Kliniken, Innsbruck, Austria

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13 #Corresponding author: Romuald Bellmann, MD, associate professor, Division of Intensive
14 Care and Emergency Medicine, Department of Internal Medicine I, Medical University of
15 Innsbruck, Anichstrasse 35, 6020 Innsbruck, Austria, Europe, romuald.bellmann@i-med.ac.at

16 **Abstract**

17 Concentrations of anidulafungin and micafungin were determined in eight different tissues
18 obtained during autopsy of four deceased who had been treated with anidulafungin and of
19 seven who had obtained micafungin. The highest amounts were recovered from liver with
20 anidulafungin concentrations of 11.01 – 66.50 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and micafungin levels of 0.36 – 5.53 $\mu\text{g/g}$
21 (0.65 $\mu\text{g/g}$ 30 days after the last administration). The lowest anidulafungin levels were
22 measured in skeletal muscle, lowest micafungin concentrations in kidney.

23

24 **Keywords:** Echinocandins, antifungal target-site penetration, tissue distribution, invasive
25 candidiasis

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27 The echinocandins anidulafungin and micafungin are recommended for treatment of invasive
28 candidiasis, because they are highly effective against candidemia (1-5). However, knowledge
29 on their concentrations in various human tissues is scarce (6, 7). Therefore, we quantified
30 anidulafungin and micafungin concentrations in eight tissues of deceased adults.

31 The study protocol was approved by the local ethics committee. Tissue samples were obtained
32 during routine autopsies of patients, who had been treated with anidulafungin or micafungin
33 within 30 days prior to death and who on admission had granted permission for scientific use
34 of residual specimens. Between death and autopsy, the bodies were kept at 4°C for up to 85 h.
35 Anidulafungin and micafungin concentrations were quantified in thyroid, lung, myocardium,
36 spleen, liver, kidney, pancreas, and skeletal muscle. The echinocandins were extracted and
37 quantified as described previously for brain (8). In brief, 0.2 g of tissue were homogenized
38 with acetonitrile and methanol and concentrations were measured with high-performance
39 liquid chromatography and UV detection (8, 9). The external standards consisted of animal
40 tissue spiked with anidulafungin or micafungin. A lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) of
41 0.10 µg/g was achieved for anidulafungin in all tissues, but skeletal muscle (LLOQ = 0.05
42 µg/g) and for micafungin in all tissues but myocardium, kidney, and pancreas (LLOQ = 0.20
43 µg/g). The process efficiency amounted to 40 to 80 %. Post-mortem stability of echinocandins
44 was assessed by incubation of patient tissue at 4 °C for 96 h. Anidulafungin was stable in all
45 tissues and micafungin in all tissues but spleen, where the concentration declined by 39 %
46 within 96 h.

47 For statistical calculations, we used IBM SPSS® Statistics software version 26.0 (Armonk,
48 NY, USA). The significance of the differences between anidulafungin and micafungin
49 concentrations was analyzed by Mann-Whitney U test. Correlations between anidulafungin
50 and micafungin concentrations, respectively, and body weight, the daily dose, the cumulative
51 dose, the interval between the last administration and death, and the interval from death to
52 autopsy were assessed using linear regression.

53 Tissue samples were obtained from four females [69 (45 – 74) years old, median (range)] who
54 had been treated with anidulafungin, and from two females and five males [58 (38 – 76) years
55 old] who had obtained micafungin. Whereas median cumulative doses were similar in both
56 treatment groups, the median interval between the last administration and death was much
57 shorter in the anidulafungin group than in the micafungin group where it was longer than 100
58 h in most patients. This might explain the significantly higher tissue concentrations of
59 anidulafungin. Nevertheless, anidulafungin tissue concentrations of patient 2, who died 290 h
60 after the last infusion (cumulative dose 1,800 mg) exceeded micafungin tissue concentrations
61 of patient 6, who died 230 h after the last administration (cumulative dose 5,300 mg). Linear
62 regression did not reveal any correlation between anidulafungin and micafungin
63 concentrations, and the analyzed demographic characteristics and treatment parameters.

64 The highest amounts of anidulafungin were recovered from the liver, followed by spleen,
65 lung, and pancreas (median >10 µg/g, Table 1). In kidney, thyroid, myocardium, and skeletal
66 muscle, anidulafungin concentrations were lower (median <10 µg/g, Table 1). The highest
67 micafungin concentrations were measured in liver, thyroid, and lung (median >0.25 µg/g,
68 Table 2). Lower concentrations were found in myocardium, skeletal muscle, and kidney
69 (median <0.20 µg/g, Table 2). Twelve days after the last administration, anidulafungin was
70 detected in all tissues of patient 2, and concentrations between 0.51 and 11.01 µg/g were
71 determined. Notably, in the liver of patient 5, micafungin could be measured even 30 days
72 after the last administration (0.65 µg/g).

73 Invasive candidiasis may affect various tissues, causing deep-seated candidiasis.

74 Anidulafungin tissue concentrations approached or even exceeded therapeutic plasma levels
75 (6). From our study population, however, no plasma levels were available.

76 MIC values of anidulafungin and micafungin range from 0.008 to 2.0 µg/ml for most
77 pathogenic *Candida* isolates (10). Anidulafungin tissue concentrations exceeded these values
78 in almost all tissue samples.

79 The limited size and the heterogeneity of our study population are considerable limitations.
80 We cannot rule out agonal or postmortem changes of echinocandin tissue concentrations.
81 However, after a 96-h incubation at 4 °C, concentrations remained unchanged in all tissues
82 but spleen. Nevertheless, patients 6 and 10 presented comparatively low micafungin
83 concentrations in their tissue samples taken 85 h and 80 h after death, respectively.
84 Furthermore, echinocandin extraction from autopsy samples might be slightly less effective
85 than extraction from calibrators. In rats treated with [¹⁴C] anidulafungin, however, tissue
86 concentrations were comparable (11). Anidulafungin and micafungin display a plasma protein
87 binding of 99.0 % and 99.9 %, respectively. Their binding to protein in tissue is unknown, but
88 protein binding influences echinocandin activity *in-vitro* (12, 13). Autopsy samples comprise
89 different tissue compartments such as extracellular matrix, various cells, and blood vessels.
90 With our method, we could not detect echinocandins on a cellular or sub-cellular level.
91 In brain samples taken from our study population we had measured anidulafungin
92 concentrations of 0.21 – 2.34 µg/g and micafungin concentrations of 0.18 – 2.88 µg/g. These
93 data have been reported previously together with concentrations in cerebrospinal fluid of
94 critically ill patients, which were even lower than brain concentrations (8). Preclinical studies
95 revealed anidulafungin and micafungin tissue concentrations and distribution comparable
96 with our findings, but in rodents, highest concentrations were measured in lung (11, 14-16).
97 Clinical studies of broncho-alveolar lavage demonstrated echinocandin accumulation in
98 alveolar macrophages (17-20). In ascites fluid and in pleural effusion, anidulafungin
99 concentrations exceeded those in cerebrospinal fluid, but were below plasma levels and the
100 MICs of some pathogenic *Candida* strains (21). Human tissue distribution of amphotericin B
101 displays a pattern similar to anidulafungin and micafungin with accumulation in liver and
102 spleen (22-24). Fluconazole and voriconazole appear to be distributed more homogeneously
103 over different tissues (25, 26).

104 In conclusion, anidulafungin and micafungin reach high concentrations in liver, spleen, and
105 lung, whereas concentrations in myocardium and skeletal muscle are low. Evaluation of the
106 clinical impact of anidulafungin and micafungin target-site penetration warrants clinical
107 outcome studies.

108

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213 **Table 1** Patient characteristics and anidulafungin concentrations in autopsy samples

Patient no.	1	2	3	4	Median (range)
Wt (kg)	135	85	43	50	67.50 (43 – 135)
Cumulative dose (mg/kg)	5.19	21.18	34.88	24.00	22.59 (5.19 – 34.88)
Treatment duration (days)	6	7	14	11	9 (6 – 14)
Interval between last AFG administration and death (h)	32	299	11.50	29	30.50 (11.50 – 299)
Interval between death and sampling (h)	14	11	15	9	12.50 (9 – 15)
Total interval last AFG administration and sampling (h)	46	310	26.50	38	42.00 (26.50 – 310)

Main diagnoses	COPD, pneumonia	DLBCL, septic shock	DLBCL, st. p. HSCT, ileus, pneumonia	Sepsis, peritonitis after sigmoid perforation	
Indication for AFG therapy	Empiric treatment	Invasive candidiasis (candidemia)	Invasive aspergillosis (AFG treatment in combination with voriconazole)	Invasive candidiasis (candidemia)	
Anidulafungin concentration in human tissue					
Thyroid (µg/g)	2.10	1.02	9.74	12.75	5.92 (1.02 – 12.75)
Lung (µg/g)	3.56	5.08	28.76	20.31	12.69 (3.56 – 28.76)
Myocardium (µg/g)	1.21	0.98	8.17	5.25	3.23 (0.98 – 8.17)
Spleen (µg/g)	6.16	2.98	36.68	24.43	15.30 (2.98 – 36.68)

Liver ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	17.33	11.01	58.17	66.50	37.75 (11.01 – 66.50)
Kidney ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	2.72	1.25	10.23	12.67	6.47 (1.25 – 12.67)
Pancreas ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	4.08	1.97	18.92	16.77	10.43 (1.97 – 18.92)
Skeletal muscle ^a ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	1.14	0.51	n.a.	7.70	1.14 (0.51 – 7.70)

214

215 AFG, anidulafungin; COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; DLBCL, diffuse large B-
216 cell lymphoma; st. p., status post; HSCT, hematopoietic stem cell transplantation; n.a., not
217 available (sampling missed); ^a rectus abdominis muscle; lower limit of quantification for
218 thyroid, lung, myocardium, spleen, liver, kidney and pancreas is 0.10 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and for skeletal
219 muscle 0.05 $\mu\text{g/g}$.

220

Table 2 Patient characteristics and micafungin concentrations in autopsy samples

Patient no.	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	Median (range)
Wt (kg)	80	92	80	60	50	81	85	80 (50 – 92)
Cumulative dose (mg/kg)	13.75	57.61	22.50	8.33	27.00	3.70	47.06	22.50 (3.70 – 57.61)
Treatment duration (days)	19	28	18	4	9	3	39	18 (3 – 39)
Interval between last MFG	712	230	110	24	148	324	235	230 (24 – 712)

administration and death (h)								
Interval between death and sampling (h) ^a	58	85	38	74	20	80	29	58 (20 – 85)
Total interval last MFG administration and sampling (h)	770	315	148	98	168	404	264	264 (98 – 770)
Main diagnoses	Burkitt-lymphoma relapse, st. p. HSCT	Wound infection (<i>C. albicans</i>), septic shock,	Cholangiocarcinoma, biliary-pleural fistula, sepsis	St. p. LuTX, ischemic stroke, pneumonia	T-cell lymphoma, cardiogenic shock	Fungal endophthalmitis, pneumonia, COPD	St. p. LTX, hepatic artery occlusion, wound infection	

		osteomyelofibrosis						
Indication for MFG therapy	Empiric treatment	Invasive candidiasis (candidemia)	Invasive candidiasis (pleural empyema)	Empiric treatment	Empiric treatment	Invasive candidiasis (<i>Candida</i> endophthalmitis)	Suspected (<i>Candida</i> cholangitis)	
Micafungin concentration in human tissue								
Thyroid (µg/g)	<0.10	0.43	0.47	0.44	<0.10	<0.10	0.44	0.43 (<0.10 – 0.47)
Lung (µg/g)	<0.10	0.20	0.70	1.81	0.23	0.18	0.29	0.26 (<0.10 – 1.81)

Myocardium (µg/g)	<0.20	<0.20	0.45	0.44	<0.20	<0.20	0.24	0.19 (<0.20 – 0.45)
Spleen (µg/g)	<0.10	0.13	0.73	1.44	<0.10	<0.10	0.31	0.22 (<0.10 – 1.44)
Liver (µg/g)	0.65	3.14	5.53	2.57	0.36	0.36	3.31	2.86 (0.36 – 5.53)
Kidney (µg/g)	<0.20	<0.20	0.50	0.77	<0.20	<0.20	<0.20	0.13 (<0.20 – 0.77)
Pancreas (µg/g)	<0.20	<0.20	0.46	0.26	<0.20	<0.20	0.44	0.15 (<0.20 – 0.46)
Skeletal muscle ^a (µg/g)	<0.10	1.78	0.18	0.13	<0.10	<0.10	0.18	0.16

								($<0.10 - 1.78$)
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MFG, micafungin; st. p., status post; HSCT, hematopoietic stem cell transplantation; *C. albicans*, *Candida albicans*; LuTX, lung transplantation;

COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; LTX, liver transplantation; ^a rectus abdominis muscle; lower limit of quantification for thyroid, lung,

spleen, liver and skeletal muscle is 0.10 µg/g and for myocardium, kidney and pancreas 0.20 µg/g.